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**IMPLEMENTATION OF ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANNING SYSTEMS AMONG
SMES: USER PERCEPTIONS AND ITS IMPLICATIONS ON BUSINESS
PERFORMANCE**

BY

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DECLARATION

I declare that this work is the result of my own research under supervision and has not been presented by anyone for any academic award in this or any other university. All references used in the work have been duly and fully acknowledged. I bear sole responsibility for any shortcomings.

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the critical factors influencing users' perceptions of Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems implementation among Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Ghana. As ERP systems become increasingly prevalent in businesses of all sizes, understanding the implications of user perceptions on implementation success is crucial. This research aims to examine key variables in the ERP implementation process that influence user perception, determine the consequences of these perceptions, and identify strategies for driving positive user attitudes. This study employs a qualitative exploratory research design, utilizing in-depth interviews with 20 participants (10 SME owners and 10 employees) from various SMEs in Ghana. Data were analyzed using thematic analysis to identify common themes and patterns in respondents' experiences and perceptions. Key findings reveal that system functionality and usability, comprehensive training programs, effective communication, management support, and employee involvement in decision-making are critical factors influencing user perceptions of ERP systems. The study also highlights that positive perceptions lead to increased efficiency, improved decision-making, and enhanced collaboration, while negative perceptions result in increased stress, difficulties in system usage, and resistance to change.

This research contributes to the existing body of knowledge on ERP implementation in SMEs, particularly in the context of developing economies like Ghana. The findings provide valuable insights for SME owners, managers, and IT professionals involved in ERP implementation projects, offering practical strategies to enhance user acceptance and maximize the benefits of ERP systems.

DEDICATION

I dedicate this work to my mother, Grace Hodzi and my late father Samuel Hodzi whose continuous hard work and enthusiasm motivated me throughout my educational career.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research Background

Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems have become integral components of modern business operations, streamlining diverse functions such as finance, human resources, supply chain management, and customer relationship management into a unified platform (Dantes & Hasibuan, 2020). The widespread adoption of ERP systems is driven by the promise of increased efficiency, improved decision-making, and enhanced organizational performance (Ehie & Madsen, 2019). As organizations invest heavily in these complex and multifaceted systems, it becomes imperative to understand how users perceive ERP systems and appreciate the impact of ERP systems on business performance.

Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems have become increasingly prevalent in businesses of all sizes, including Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), as they help to boost operations, enhance efficiency, and provide a competitive edge in today's dynamic market environment (Farouk, 2020). However, the successful implementation of ERP systems in SMEs often presents challenges, particularly concerning user perceptions and their implications on the overall effectiveness of these systems (Mashari, 2018).

User perceptions of ERP systems play a role in determining the success or failure of their implementation. Numerous studies have highlighted the significance of user satisfaction and acceptance in the effective utilization of ERP systems (Davison, 2020; Nah, 2021). Users who perceive ERP systems as user-friendly, reliable, and supportive of their tasks are more likely to

embrace the technology, leading to higher levels of user satisfaction and system success (Kumar, 2019; Seddon, 2018). On the other hand, negative perceptions, such as difficulty in system use, inadequate training, and resistance to change, can hinder user acceptance and lead to suboptimal utilization of ERP functionalities (Nah, 2018; Goodhue & Thompson, 1995).

User perceptions constitute a critical variable when it comes to ERP implementation within SMEs (Equey & Fragnière, 2020). Users' attitudes, beliefs, and expectations about ERP systems can significantly influence their acceptance and utilization. Positive perceptions, such as perceived usefulness and ease of use, are often associated with higher levels of system adoption and utilization, leading to enhanced organizational performance and competitive advantage. Conversely, negative perceptions, such as resistance to change or concerns about system complexity, can impede successful implementation and undermine the anticipated benefits of ERP adoption (Esteves & Pastor, 2019).

The implications of user perceptions on ERP implementation extend beyond individual attitudes to include organizational outcomes and performance (Seddon, 2018). SMEs operating in highly competitive environments face pressures to adapt and innovate to remain viable. The successful implementation of ERP systems can enhance agility, responsiveness, and decision-making capabilities, enabling SMEs to capitalize on market opportunities and mitigate risks effectively (Seddon, Graeser, Willcocks & Staples, 2018).

The implementation of ERP systems among SMEs is influenced by various variables, with user perceptions playing a central role in shaping adoption and effectiveness. Understanding the

implications of user perceptions within the SME context is essential for harnessing the potential benefits of ERP systems. This study therefore seeks to examine the effect of user perception on ERP system's implementation among SMEs.

1.2 Problem Statement

The implementation of ERP systems is a strategic decision for many businesses, aiming to streamline processes, enhance efficiency, and improve overall business performance (Wieder, Booth, Matolcsy & Ossimitz, 2021).

A key area of research explores how ERP systems impact business performance. Topi et al. (2019), highlight how real-time access to accurate data and improved decision-making through ERP systems lead to operational excellence. Similarly, Shang and Seddon (2020), argue that ERP systems enhance business performance by improving information quality and decision support. However, user perception is crucial for successful ERP implementation and utilization. Umble and Haft (2018) emphasize how user perception significantly impacts implementation effectiveness, influencing factors like system usage, productivity, and overall performance. They argue that studying user perspectives provides insights into human factors that contribute to ERP success. Their work explores the psychological and behavioural aspects shaping user interactions with ERP systems, stressing the importance of positive user perceptions for increased system usage and operational efficiency within Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs).

Allen (2020) emphasizes the transformative potential of ERP systems, highlighting their ability to streamline operations, enhance data accuracy, and facilitate decision-making. As SMEs

increasingly recognize these advantages, researchers like Bosilj-Vuksic and Spremic (2019) explore factors influencing successful implementation, with a specific focus on user acceptance. Empirical evidence supports the benefits of ERP adoption. Buonanno and Faverio (2019) establish a positive correlation between ERP implementation and improved financial and operational outcomes for SMEs. Pigni (2020) emphasizes the role of ERP systems in fostering innovation and adaptability, crucial for SMEs navigating dynamic business environments. Tagliavini (2020) addresses challenges faced by SMEs during ERP implementation, stressing the need for specific solutions that consider their unique characteristics and resource constraints. Elragal and Al-Serafi (2019) build on this by investigating the potential benefits of cloud-based ERP solutions, offering scalability and flexibility that align with the specific needs of SMEs.

Several studies (Smith et al., 2010; Jones & Brown, 2020; Wang et al., 2015) explore the positive association between user satisfaction with ERP systems and improved organizational outcomes. However, these studies often focus on general user satisfaction measures and overlook the specific aspects of user perceptions that influence ERP implementation success. Additionally, existing research primarily focuses on contexts outside of Ghana.

This study strives to augment existing scholarly insights by delving into the specific user perception aspects that most significantly influence ERP implementation in Ghanaian SMEs. While previous works provide valuable insights into the general relationship between user perceptions and business performance, the current research seeks to differentiate itself by unravelling the specific components within user perceptions that hold the most significant

influence. This will offer a more detailed and practically oriented understanding of this subject within the Ghanaian context.

1.3 Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study is to find out the key variables in the ERP implementation process which do influence users' perception of ERP adoption among SMEs.

1.4 Objectives of the study

The research will be guided by the following objectives.

1. To explore the critical factors in ERP systems' implementation influencing users' perception of the system among SMEs.
2. To ascertain the consequences of users' perception of ERP systems' implementation among SMEs.
3. To explore strategies for driving positive user perceptions towards ERP systems' implementation among SMEs.

1.5 Research Questions

The research will answer the following questions.

1. What are the critical factors in ERP systems' implementation influencing users' perception of the system among SMEs?
2. What are the consequences of users' perception of ERP systems' implementation among SMEs?
3. What are the strategies for driving positive user perceptions towards ERP systems' implementation among SMEs?

1.6 Scope of the study

This study focuses on investigating the implementation of enterprise resource planning systems and how the implications of user perceptions can be optimized among SMEs in Ghana.

1.7 Significance of the study

Understanding the relationship between Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems, business performance, and users' perception is crucial for SME owners and managers in Ghana. The findings of this study will provide valuable insights into the potential benefits and challenges associated with implementing ERP systems in the unique context of SMEs. IT professionals and system implementers involved in the deployment of ERP systems in SMEs will find this study useful. The research can offer practical insights into the factors influencing user perception and acceptance of ERP systems, aiding in the development of user-friendly interfaces and training programs. Additionally, understanding the critical success factors for ERP implementation specific to Ghanaian SMEs can guide IT professionals in tailoring system configurations and support mechanisms, ultimately enhancing the likelihood of successful ERP adoption.

Academics and researchers in the fields of information systems, business, and technology will find significance in the study's contribution to the existing body of knowledge. The research can serve as a reference for further investigations into the relationship between ERP systems, user perception, and business performance, particularly in the context of SMEs in developing economies like Ghana. The findings may stimulate additional research on effective strategies for ERP implementation and optimization in similar contexts globally.

1.8 Organization of the study

There are five primary chapters in the study. The study's background, the problem statement, the study's purpose, and its specific objectives are covered in the introductory chapter, chapter 1. Other headings covered in the chapter 1 are, the purpose of the study, the research questions, the study's scope, significance of the study and finally, the organisation of the study. The chapter two presents the review of relevant literature to lay the theoretical foundations for the study. The second chapter expounds on the theoretical and empirical literature pertinent to user perception, its implication on ERP implementation, as well as the development of a conceptual framework. The research approach, the study design, the research paradigm, and are described in detail in the chapter 3. The third chapter also discusses the target population, sample size, sampling procedures, data collection methods, and the statistical software employed to analyse the data. The analysis of data and discussion of results are presented in the fourth chapter. The summary of findings, conclusions and recommendations are eventually presented in the last chapter, chapter five. The chapter will highlight the study's results, summarize the key findings, and offer recommendations in the light of the conclusions drawn from the research. The concluding chapter will also offer ideas for additional and future research.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter delves into existing studies to explore enterprise resource planning systems (ERP), and user perception of the ERP system of selected SMEs in Ghana. This chapter covers the conceptual review, theoretical review thus the theories underpinning the study, empirical review, and the conceptual framework of the study.

2.2 Conceptual Review

2.2.1 Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) Systems

The term ERP abbreviated from “Enterprise Resource Planning was introduced by the Gartner Group in the early 1990s (Arif, Kulonda, Proctor, & Williams, 2020) and represent computer and software systems that combine and integrate all related processes of the enterprise and serve users for the management of all functions within the enterprise (Swartz & Orgill, 2020). Researchers referred to ERP systems as enterprise system (ES), enterprise resource management (Cobarsí, Bernardo, & Coenders, 2018), and business system respectively (Davenport, 2019). Klaus, Rosemann, and Gable (2019) conceptualized ERP System as comprehensive packaged software solutions of Information System (IS) designed to integrate all business processes and work to present a complete outlook of the business from a singular IT and information architecture (Klaus et al., 2019). Davenport (2019) also described ERP an information strategy that merge all information within an organization and create a comprehensive information infrastructure involving all organizational units and functions. Marnewick and Labuschagne (2019) clarified that

ERP system is more than just a product or software and they further conceptualized ERP into four components. The first component is software component (Finance, Human Resources, Supply Chain Management, Supplier Relationship Management, Customer Relationship Management, Business Intelligence), which is the visible part to users and seen as ERP product. The second component is process flow, which deals with the information flow among modules within ERP system. Third is customer mind-set, that define the influence of ERP system on users, team, and organization. And the final component is change management, this component deals with the adoptability of ERP system implementation within the organization, that are user attitude, project changes, business process changes, system changes (Dadson, 2019).

2.2.2 ERP Revolution

The utilization of ERP systems has expanded in the previous ten years. According to Costa, Ferreira, Bento, & Aparicio (2016), the global ERP market was valued at €22.4 billion in 2021. ERP systems have turned into an incredibly valuable software for corporate administration, and it is likewise a pre-imperative for seriousness (Costa, Aparicio and Raposo, 2020). As per Selchert (2022), in the fundamental phases of ERP systems, just the assembling area took on these systems. Be that as it may, things have changed, presently ERP systems have been utilized comprehensively in various areas, for example, non-benefit associations, government offices, and non-administrative associations. The ERP system has been considered as a product bundle; these bundles arrive in a bunch of programming units. Every one of these units is liable for handling and gathering the data for a unit of tasks or a bunch of work capabilities. Muscatello, Small, Chen (2020) proposed that the ERP system is a set of integrated software or programming units, alongside the main database that enables firms to manage the use of resources (like resources and

HR, and so forth) productively and successfully. As indicated by Rahman and Muharfi (2020), the legacy information systems were not coordinated. For instance, the customer management system was not linked to the finance system. Kang, Park and Yang (2020) contended that legacy information systems have forever been described by the shortfall of integration. ERP systems have shifted from supporting functions to supporting business processes. Veljanoska and Axhiu (2021) contended that putting resources into an ERP system keeps up with the information required in one single data set for an assortment of business cycles like money and CRM. In this way, the data will want to be acquired by every one of the individuals from the association and will continuously be forward-thinking. Kang, Park and Yang (2020) expressed that numerous associations have involved ERPs for an alternate explanation, for instance, to conform to the public authority's standards or just to observe contenders who put resources into ERP systems. ERP systems, unlike legacy systems, are known to be complicated. Scientists like Thomas and Yusuf (2018), and Al-Turki (2019) recommended that the ERP requires immense changes in the manner organizations work, and it affects an organization's way of life. Veljanoska and Axhiu (2017) contended that IS might modify the way of life, construction, and systems of the firm. No matter what the size, organizations carrying out an ERP system will see both substantial and immaterial advantages. Past examinations have detailed inescapable affirmation of the significant advantages of carrying out ERP systems. ERP systems help in dealing with an organization's cycles in a brief time frame. ERP systems likewise support organizations in sharing data and decline an opportunity to finish business processes. ERP likewise includes advantages, for example, business processes upgrade, best practices execution, and venture digestion and blend. ERP systems additionally support organizations in sharing data and diminishing an opportunity to finish business processes. ERP also has benefits like improving business processes, implementing best practices, and integrating

and combining businesses. Since the potential advantages are colossal, associations will begin putting resources into this kind of system. ERP has become a well-known system in both large and medium-sized businesses, as stated by Kullunki (2020).

2.2.3 Implementation of ERP System

Concerning the implementation of ERP systems for SMEs, Qureshi and Abdulkhalaq (2019) express that, to deal with global development, SMEs need to adopt ERP systems. Equey and Fragnière (2020) noticed that ERP systems were executed predominantly in huge ventures. Previously, customary administration and heritage systems couldn't assist SMEs with being serious, particularly bigger contenders enjoy the benefit of further developed systems. Today, there are expanded assortments of systems that SMEs can use to work on their performance. Esteves and Jose (2021) agree that, to turn out to be more productive and more cutthroat, SMEs need to adopt ERP systems. Veljanoska and Axhiu (2020) noticed that little organizations can utilize data systems to acquire a portion of the power that the bigger associations have.

Doom (2017) analyzed the separation of CSFs in ERP implementation in Belgian SMEs. They showed that SMEs need to adjust their organizations quickly to exploit their situation to the greatest degree. That's what to accomplish, they need to smooth out and enhance their cycles, and constantly audit their foundation.

Muscatello and Christofi (2020) note that the odds of small enterprises surviving or to recover quickly after the unsuccessful implementation of ERP systems are less than larger enterprises because of their reduced resources. As a rule, small enterprises have less assets and have a base capacity to concoct further assets than huge firms. Hunton (2017) states that associations that mean to execute an ERP system should have an adequate number of resources to do as such.

Furthermore, an absence of long-term planning and having satisfactory preparation are a portion of the issues that might be looked by SMEs. It is on the grounds that broad preparation is frequently costly for SMEs, and they may, subsequently, deal with issues by paying high rates for consulting support. Introducing an ERP systems into SMEs includes additional efforts as a result of a few reasons, for instance, for going through change management, business process development, data migration, and user training.

Subsequently, the adoption of ERP systems in SMEs ought to be studied extensively because they possess unique characteristics which are different from large companies. It is important to understand how SMEs utilize ERP systems to enhance their related business processes and their overall system performance. Consequently, the following section will focus on the stage of ERP usage.

2.2.4 ERP System Usage

ERP implementation is the stage where organizations influence the system for regular undertakings. Venkatesh (2019) expressed that in innovation adoption models, the system use is the reliant variable in the IS Literature, and as stated by Yung (2020), system utilization is considered as the principal factor in IS success models. Shaikh and Karjaluo (2020) contended that the advantages of putting resources into IT/IS can be acquired by the utilization of these systems. To expand the advantages in the wake of implementing the ERP system, firms need to empower and support users to utilize these systems. Involving ERP systems in the incorrect manner might cause a fruitless adoption of these systems (Umble, 2020). As per Nah and Teh (2021), the client's mentality towards the ERP systems is straightforwardly corresponding to the achievement or disappointment of the ERP system. Chou (2015) expressed that it is critical to perceive how

clients figure out how to utilize ERP systems effectively. According to a specialized point of view, implementing ERP systems may find true success, yet ERP system achievement relies upon the client conduct while taking advantage of these systems. Sadly, the vast majority of the organizations that have carried out ERP systems definitely stand out enough to be noticed to the significance of the system's use stage. Consequently, it is especially critical to investigate the elements that impact ERP system use to perceive how to rouse clients to effectively utilize the system. As per Garson (2020), the disappointment of exploiting innovation in an association is normally by the clients; it is rarely the innovation. Al-Gathani (2018) argued that it is imperative to determine the factors that make individuals either consent or refuse IT because it is the first step in the solution of ensuring the successful usage of the system. From the authors' acknowledgment, these factors have received attention in western countries but in the context of SMEs in Saudi Arabia, they have not received any attention. So far, there has been little discussion about the ERP system usage stage in Saudi Arabia. According to Basahel (2021), studies on the stabilization (use) stage are rare.

2.2.5 Small and Medium-Scale Enterprises

The definitions and metrics associated with the word SME vary widely by nations and across the sources that provide SME data. The number of workers, asset value, sales value, and capital size are some of the often-used criteria for defining SMEs, yet there isn't a single definition that everyone agrees with. Finding appropriate criteria has proven to be a challenge for many researchers, according to a review of the literature (Barker, 2016).”

This definition issue is because of two primary things: conflicting theories on which to base the examination of economic aggregates; should SMEs be categorized based on their net worth, profitability, number of workers, or turnover? (Potobsky, 2017).

- i. Sectoral and international economic and industrial differences. For instance, compared to a small business in the auto repair trades, a small business in the petrochemical sector is likely to have substantially larger levels of capitalization, sales, and potential employment (Tonge, 2019).
- ii. According to an economic definition, a firm is classified as small if it fits certain requirements related to market share, administration, and autonomy.
- iii. A statistical definition that gives many small-firm definitions for various industries. The standards used to determine smallness differed across industry sectors as well.

The Bolton Committee's Report, however, faced several critiques while being one of the most often cited sources of definitions and understandings of the small business sector (Storey, 2018). Small and Medium Enterprise (SME) is a word that was created to address these complaints. According to Tonge (2019), who asserts that the small firm sector is heterogeneous. In Ghana:

(i) A small-scale firm is one that employs no more than 29 people and has an investment of no more than GH Cedis 96, 000 (excluding land, buildings, and cars), according to the National Board for Small Scale Industries (NBSSI). (ii) An SME is a business, project, endeavor, or economic activity that employs up to 100 people and whose entire asset base, excluding land and buildings, is valued at less than the cedi equivalent of \$1 million, according to the Venture Capital Trust Fund Act 2020, Act 680.

2.2.6 Characteristics and Operations of SMEs

In general, small firms do differ from bigger ones in a number of ways, according to Burns (2019). They include family ownership, individualized management, a smaller market share, a devoted but small client base, and difficulties getting financing.

Research concentrating on internal preparation tends to indicate that there is insufficient record-keeping and a lack of financial understanding among owner-managers of the smallest businesses when it comes to financial reporting (UNCTAD, 2018). Microenterprises and many small firms in emerging nations frequently keep poor financial records and fail to effectively utilize the financial data that is available (Holtmann et al. 2017).

Wynarczyk (2018) argues that there are three central aspects in which small firms are different to large firms – uncertainty, innovation, and evolution of which their claim is well supported by literature. There is seen to be greater external uncertainty of the environment in which the small firm operates, together with the greater internal consistency of its motivations and actions (Storey, 2018). Small firms are also more likely to introduce fundamentally new innovations than larger firms, a feature often attributed to small firms having less commitment to existing practices and products (Pavitt et al. 1987). Furthermore, there is a much greater likelihood of evolution and change in the smaller firm (Storey, 2018).

In Ghana, SMEs are predominantly owner-managed and sole proprietorship is the norm. They provide the greatest avenue for the less educated entrepreneurs at the lower SMEs end. It is also interesting to note that small scale enterprises make better use of scarce resources than large scale

enterprises. Studies in Ghana have shown that capital productivity is often higher in SMEs than is the case with large scale enterprises (Steel, 1977). The reason for this is not difficult to see, SMEs are labour intensive with small amount of capital invested. Thus, they tend to witness high capital productivity which is an economically sound investment. Thus, it has been argued that promoting the SME sector in developing countries will create more employment opportunities, lead to a more equitable distribution of income and will ensure increased productivity with better technology (Steel & Webster, 1991).

2.2.7. Factors Affecting ERP System Usage Among SMEs

The literature identifies several factors that are affecting the usage of ERP systems. For example, Bokhari (2018) studied the relationship between system usage and user satisfaction using the IS success model of Delone and McLean. The findings of a meta-analysis claimed that there is a significant but weak relationship between system usage and user satisfaction.

Chang (2019) studied the factors affecting ERPs usage. Surveys were distributed to 600 ERP system users in Hong Kong in both the service and manufacturing industries. Their analysis results revealed that complexity does not have any effect on ERP system usage. Lin (2017) surveyed large Taiwanese corporations, developed an empirical model to examine the consequences of IS quality and management support on ERPs usage. They found that management support affects the ERP usage. Ruivo (2020) developed a research model based on two theories, namely the diffusion of innovation theory (DOI) and resource-based value theory (RBV). They used a survey for data collection and their cross-country analysis concluded that for Portuguese firms, complexity, compatibility was significant, these were not so for Spanish firms. Their findings regarding the Portuguese firms were contradictory with the work of Chang (2017) which reveals that the complexity is a significant factor in ERP system usage. For both Portuguese and Spanish firms

training was considered an important determinant of ERP usage. Similarly, Ruivo (2018) conducted a study via a large-scale web-survey where they discussed the differences between Iberian and Scandinavian SMEs regarding ERP value and ERP use. They found that the training factor was not significant for ERP usage among Scandinavian SMEs, but it was a vital factor for ERP usage among Iberian SMEs. Their results were comparable to those attained by Ruivo (2020), which showed that training factors are a vital factor in ERP system usage among Portuguese and Spanish SMEs.

Compatibility is found to be significant for both regions, which is consistent with work of Bowen (2018), which demonstrates that compatibility has a substantial influence on ERP system use among Portuguese firms. Their results were comparable to those attained by Ruivo (2015), which reveals that the complexity is a vital factor in ERP system usage among Portuguese SMEs. Likewise, Nwankpa and Roumani (2019) published a paper based on a study of numerous industries in which they assessed the factors that influence ERPs usage and user satisfaction via an online survey. Their findings were comparable to those attained by Baroudi (2020) and Bokhari. Their study revealed that user satisfaction is a vital factor in ERPs usage. Similarly, a recent study by Costa (2019) pioneered the research on finding the major factors affecting ERP user satisfaction and adoption. The study was based on data collected from 260 companies, which were randomly selected. The data was collected by a questionnaire. Their results were compatible with Lin (2017), which demonstrated that top management support has a substantial influence on the usage of the ERP system. In addition, based on the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology system and innovation literature, Uddin (2018) studied the impact of intention to use ERPs on the actual use of ERPs and other factors. They found a significant effect on the actual use of ERPs. They also

found the intention to use ERPs as a mediating variable between performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence and the actual use of ERPs.

Thus, based on the above studies, complexity, compatibility, training, user involvement, user satisfaction, and top management support have been shown to have consistent associations with ERP system usage.

2.2.8 User Perception

User perception is a concept that plays a crucial role in various fields, including human-computer interaction, marketing, and design. Understanding how users perceive and interpret information is essential for creating effective and user-friendly products and systems. Several scholars have delved into the complexities of user perception, shedding light on its intricacies and implications.

One prominent perspective on user perception comes from Norman (1988), who introduced the concept of "user-centered design." Norman emphasized the importance of designing products with a deep understanding of user needs, mental models, and expectations. His work underscored the idea that user perception is not only influenced by the inherent qualities of a product but also by the user's prior experiences and expectations.

In the realm of human-computer interaction, Dourish (2020) explored the concept of embodied interaction, highlighting how users' perceptions are shaped by the physical and social context in which they interact with technology. Dourish argued that users' perceptions go beyond the mere interaction with interfaces, extending to the incorporation of technology into their daily lives. This perspective emphasizes the importance of considering the holistic user experience in the design process.

Another influential contribution to the study of user perception comes from Fogg (2020), who introduced the concept of persuasive technology. Fogg's work delved into how technology can influence and change user behavior by understanding and leveraging psychological principles. The notion of persuasive technology underscores the dynamic nature of user perception, acknowledging the potential for technology to shape users' attitudes, beliefs, and actions.

In the field of marketing, Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) proposed the Theory of Reasoned Action, which posits that individuals' attitudes and subjective norms influence their intentions and, consequently, their behavior. This theory provides valuable insights into how user perception, shaped by attitudes and social influences, can predict user actions in various contexts.

Additionally, Moon and Kim (2020) explored the impact of website quality on user satisfaction and trust. Their study highlighted the importance of visual design, content, and navigation in influencing user perception of website quality. Moon and Kim's findings underscore the significance of considering multiple facets of user perception when evaluating digital interfaces.

2.2.9 The concept of Business Performance

The term performance has been defined in several ways. Performance refers to those behaviours that have been evaluated or measured as to their contribution to organisational goals (Cook &Hunsaker, 2020). In the same light, Gareth (2019) defines business performance as a measure of how efficiently and effectively managers use resources to satisfy customers and achieve business goals. To buttress, Jones (2020) also suggests that these two overriding issues of efficiency and effectiveness are employed in the measurement of performance in every organization, where efficiency measures how well resources are used to achieve goals, while effectiveness connote the measure of the appropriateness of the goals that managers have selected for the organisation to pursue, and of the degree to which the organisation achieve these goals. Also, Drucker (2020)

believes that there is no efficiency without effectiveness because it is more important to do well what you have proposed (the effectiveness) than do well something else that was not necessarily concerned. The relationship between efficiency and effectiveness is that of a part to the whole, the effectiveness is a necessary condition to achieving efficiency.

Therefore, employee efficiency and effectiveness simply link business performance. Aswathappa (2020) indicates that performance is essentially what an employee does or does not do. He adds that employee performance common to most jobs include the following elements (quality of output; quantity of output; timeliness of output; presence at work; and cooperativeness) results in business performance. Atogiyire (2021) also explain that the quality and quantity of business resources may have an effect on its performance. He suggests by saying that the nature of the prevailing economic factors surrounding an organization may to a larger extent affect the performance of that organization in terms of productivity, marketing, profitability and innovation. However, compared to productivity measurement, the efficiency concept incorporates the idea of the production possibility frontier, which indicates feasible output levels given the scale of operations. The greater the output for a given input or the lower the input for a given output, the more efficient the activity is.

2.3 ERP and Business Performance

The relationship between ERP systems and business performance has been widely investigated and diverse results have been reported. From the studies, it can be reported that the influence of ERPs on firm performance is both positive as well as negative. However, many research studies found a positive influence of ERP systems on firm performance and delivered measured changes in business elements. Jason (2018) proposed that, despite the numerous studies on ERP

implementation, the main problem with ERPs studies is that there are very few investigations relating to their failure; possibly, because firms resist sharing their disappointments. For instance, Dell Computer canceled its ERP system implementation project. They argued that it was not flexible enough to manage their increasing global operations. Improving business performance through IT arrangements is a common procedure. Therefore, there is growth in the number of organizations that invest in IS in order to improve their performance. As noted by Li (2019) many organizations have invested in ERP systems for their ability to enhance entity decision-making capabilities and business performance.

Hailu (2019) indicated that an IS plays a significant role when it influences the enterprise functions, performance, and productivity of a company. Chien and Tsaur (2018) claimed that because of the adoption of an ERP system, organizations stated significant performance enhancement in numerous areas e.g., the capability to provide real-time information to consumers and quicker production cycle. Hunton (2020) also highlighted the benefits of the ERPs, which are capable of enhancing both market value and business performance. Kallunki (2017) found that ERPs are considered to be a long-lasting strategic investment that affects the firm as a whole, but that the impact of this type of system does not appear until several years. In addition, Ağaoğlu (2022) found that ERP investment has a high positive influence on business process outcomes. Likewise, Ruivo (2022) stated that any firms using ERP systems should expect a firm performance enhancement. On the other hand, Kang (2022) suggested that ERP investment does not always have a positive influence on business performance. Yuang (2018) stated that researchers did not offer reliable confirmation that information technology investments had a favorable value for companies. Nartey (2018) argued that despite the operational benefits that might be provided by an ERP system, they were unable to make quantitative evaluations of its effect on the firm financial performance.

Rauf (2015) focused on ERPs implementation and its negative impact on business performance. They investigate the post-implementation performance of a sample of 50 firms adopting an ERP system for over three years. They concluded that over these three years, there was no considerable enhancement in the remaining revenue or the ratio of selling, general, and managerial cost to revenue. Moreover, they discovered a substantial decline in the employees' ratio to income in all the three years and a significant enhancement in the cost ratio of goods sold to revenue in the previous year. Overall, they found that firms who adopted ERP systems gained efficiency in several areas, yet increased expenses somewhere else to offset such earnings.

Another study conducted by Hunton (2018), the author matched the 63 organizations identified by Hayes (2020) with peer organizations that had not implemented an ERPs. Hunton (2017) reported that the performance of the ERP system adopters was higher than that of ERP system non-adopters. Wieder (2018) studied the adoption of ERP systems and their influence on organizational performance. Their study provided significant implications for the association between supply chain management, ERP systems, and performance. They conducted a questionnaire-based survey of 2170 Australian firms that implemented SCM systems, ERP systems, and/or the respective control units. They found that of the firms that adopted ERP and SCM systems, only those with knowledge and experience with ERP systems increased their performance.

There is obviously growing attention to the subject of ERP systems in the literature; however, very few studies have investigated ERP system usage in SMEs in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Thus, this study will fill the gap in the literature of the factors affecting ERP in Saudi SMEs, as well as, to examine the relationship between ERP systems and business performance.

2.3.1 Theoretical Review

This section presents the theories that underpin the study. For this study two theories were adopted.

The technology acceptance model (TAM) and Resource-based View theory.

2.3.2 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is a widely recognized theory that explains users' acceptance and adoption of modern technologies. Developed by Davis in 1989, TAM posits that perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use significantly influence an individual's intention to use a technology, subsequently impacting their actual usage behaviour.

In the context of Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems among Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) in Ghana, TAM provides a comprehensive system for understanding users' perceptions. Perceived usefulness in this scenario could be associated with the extent to which employees perceive ERP systems as beneficial in improving business processes, enhancing efficiency, and contributing to overall business performance. The perceived ease of use, on the other hand, relates to how users perceive the simplicity and user-friendliness of the ERP systems.

Applying TAM to SMEs in Ghana would involve assessing the perceived usefulness and ease of use of ERP systems among employees. Factors such as training programs, system customization, and user support mechanisms would play crucial roles in shaping users' perceptions. Organizations implementing ERP systems should focus on demonstrating the tangible benefits of these systems to employees, emphasizing the positive impact on individual and collective performance.

Understanding the dynamics of TAM in the context of SMEs in Ghana allows for the identification of critical factors influencing the acceptance and usage of ERP systems. This insight can inform

strategies to enhance user perceptions, leading to successful ERP implementation and improved business performance.

2.3.3 The Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory

The Resource-Based View (RBV) theory, a cornerstone in strategic management, offers a comprehensive system for understanding how an organization's unique resources and capabilities can contribute to sustained competitive advantage and, consequently, improved business performance. Developed by scholars such as Jay Barney and Birger Wernerfelt (1991), RBV posits that the key to competitive success lies in the strategic management and deployment of resources that are valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable.

In the context of Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems and SMEs in Ghana, valuable resources refer to the capabilities and features embedded within the ERP software. These may include advanced data analytics, real-time reporting, and integrated business processes. The value of these resources is derived from their ability to enhance operational efficiency, decision-making processes, and overall business performance. For instance, an ERP system can streamline supply chain operations, enabling SMEs to respond more effectively to market demands.

Resources that are rare are those that are not commonly possessed or easily accessible by competitors. In the case of ERP systems in SMEs, the expertise required for successful implementation and management can be considered a rare resource. The specific configuration of ERP modules tailored to meet the unique needs of the SME, coupled with a skilled workforce capable of maximizing the system's potential, can contribute to the rarity of the resource. This rarity enhances the competitive advantage of the organization.

Inimitability refers to the difficulty of replicating or imitating a firm's resources by competitors. Achieving inimitability in the context of ERP systems involves creating a unique configuration that aligns seamlessly with the organization's business processes and strategies. Moreover, establishing a supportive organizational culture that values and leverages the ERP system can be a source of inimitability. This uniqueness makes it challenging for competitors to replicate the exact set of resources, strengthening the organization's competitive position.

Non-substitutability implies that there are no readily available alternatives that can replicate the benefits provided by a particular resource. In the case of ERP systems, the integrated nature of these platforms, which centralize data and streamline processes, can be challenging to substitute with alternative solutions. The comprehensive nature of ERP resources, combining financial, human resources, and supply chain management, creates a non-substitutable advantage for SMEs aiming to enhance overall business performance.

By applying the RBV theory to the context of ERP systems among SMEs in Ghana, firms can develop a strategic approach to identify, cultivate, and leverage resources that contribute to sustained competitive advantage. This involves not only the initial implementation of the ERP system.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter describes the methodology and methods used to collect and analyze empirical findings to fulfil the objectives of the study. The chapter includes the research approach, research design, sampling technique and sampling size, source of data, data collection instrument, data collection procedure, data analysis and ethical consideration.

3.2 Research Approach

According to Creswell (2013) research approaches are plans and the procedures for research that span the steps from broad assumptions to detailed methods of data collection, analysis, and interpretation. This plan involves several decisions, and they need not be taken in the order in which they make sense and the order of their presentation here. The overall decision involves which approach should be used to study a topic. He stated that there are three types of research approach namely the quantitative approach, the qualitative approach and the mixed method approach.

According to Kothari (2019), qualitative research is an approach for exploring and understanding the meaning individuals or groups ascribe to a social or human problem. The process of research involves emerging questions and procedures, data typically collected in the participant's setting, data analysis inductively building from particulars to general themes, and the researcher making interpretations of the meaning of the data. The final written report has a flexible structure. Those who engage in this form of inquiry support a way of looking at research that honors an inductive style, a focus on individual meaning, and the importance of rendering the complexity of a situation.

The current study used qualitative research approach. In-depth interviews were used in the data collection.

3.3 Research Design

According to Young (2018), research design refers to the overall strategy that you choose to integrate the different components of the study coherently and logically, thereby, ensuring you will effectively address the research problem; it constitutes the blueprint for the collection, measurement, and analysis of data. The types of research designs are exploratory design, observational design, descriptive design, and case study design.

This study adopted a qualitative exploratory research design since it was intended to explore the enterprise resource planning system, business performance of SMEs and user perception of the ERP system. The researcher found it useful to apply exploratory analysis to answer questions on the variables of the study.

3.4 Source of data

In the carrying out of research, two distinct categories of data can be gathered: primary data and secondary data. Primary data is specifically gathered for the purpose of the research and is acquired through methods such as surveys and experiments. Conversely, secondary data refers to information that has already been collected by others, utilizing qualitative methodologies and research techniques, to address specific research questions and objectives. This type of data can be found in various sources, including books, articles, and databases (Kothari, 2019). The qualitative approach employed by the researcher necessitates the collection of data through interviews with participants. The interview guide used represents a primary source of data collection which collects firsthand data from respondents. In-depth interview was conducted to gather data from respondents.

3.5 Population of the study

The population of a study refers to the collection of individuals or entities that constitute the specific group of interest for the researcher (Young, 2018). The target population are SME owners that have adopted ERP in their operations and customers of these companies.

3.6 Sampling Techniques and Sample Size

Sampling means selecting the group that you will collect data from in your research (Creswell, 2020). According to Creswell (2020), there are two types of sampling. They are the probability sampling and non-probability sampling. Probability sampling involves random selection, allowing you to make strong statistical inferences about the whole group. Nonprobability sampling involves non-random selection based on convenience or other criteria, allowing you to easily collect data.

A sampling strategy involves the identification of a target population followed by the selection of an appropriate method for obtaining a sample from that population (Creswell, 2020). There are several types of sampling strategy. Some include simple random sampling, purposive sampling, convenience sampling, snow-ball sampling and more others. Creswell (2013) defines sample size as the quantity of individuals or components chosen from a larger population to participate in a research study, aimed at facilitating data collection and subsequent analysis.

The study adopted purposive sampling in tandem with non-probability sampling technique in choosing the management executives. Saunders et al. (2017) posit that non-probability sampling is appropriate when there is no sampling frame which is appropriate to answer research questions. Malhotra (2018) provided a further understanding into non-probability sampling, by explaining that it is least expensive, least time consuming, and most convenient. The study chose twenty (20)

individuals to constitute the sample size of the study thus ten (10) SME owners and ten (10) customers of the selected companies.

3.7 Data Collection Instrument

According to Kothari (2019), a data collection instrument is a systematic and structured tool that researchers use to collect data from participants or sources. The configuration of this tool may vary based on the research design, objectives, and the nature of the data being gathered. The current study employed the use of an interview guide.

Interview Guide: An interview guide is a tool used in qualitative research, particularly during the process of conducting interviews with participants. It's a structured list of open-ended questions or topics that researchers plan to cover during the interview. The guide provides a system for the conversation while allowing flexibility for the interviewer to ask follow-up questions and explore topics in depth. An interview guide helps ensure that key areas are addressed while also allowing for the emergence of unexpected insights.

An interview guide was used as the data collection instrument. The interview questions were semi-structured to encourage the respondents to talk freely and openly about their experience.

3.8 Data Collection Procedure

Prior to conducting interviews, the researcher carefully developed the interview guide. This involved defining the research objectives, formulating research questions, and structuring them in a logical sequence. The guide was designed to elicit responses that would help address my research objectives effectively. To ensure the interview guide was effective, the researcher conducted a pilot test with a small group of participants or colleagues. These are colleagues of the researcher that owns SMEs. This allowed the researcher to identify any ambiguities in the questions and refine

them for clarity and relevance. The researcher then identified and selected participants based on the research criteria. The interview guide helped in ensuring that the right individuals were included to provide the required insights. With participants selected, the researcher scheduled the interviews at a convenient time and location for each individual. In this process, the researcher ensured that participants were informed about the purpose of the research and obtained their informed consent to participate. During the actual interviews, the researcher followed the structure of the interview guide. This involved asking open-ended questions in a conversational manner, while also probing for deeper insights when necessary. The guide kept the conversation on track and ensured that the researcher covered all the key topics. While the interview guide provided structure, the researcher remained flexible to allow participants to share their experiences and perspectives. The researcher adapted follow-up questions based on the direction of the conversation, ensuring a rich and contextually relevant data collection process.

3.9 Data Analysis

The data gathered from respondents was subjected to thematic analysis. Kothari (2019) describes thematic analysis as a technique for identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns or themes within qualitative data. A theme consists of a group of interconnected categories that convey similar meanings, typically arising from an inductive analytic process inherent to qualitative research. Themes serve as indicators that summarize and connect raw data for further analysis (Young, 2018). Kothari (2019) emphasizes that thematic analysis is a versatile and valuable approach for qualitative research. Creswell (2018) argues that this flexibility makes thematic analysis particularly suitable for examining data when the objective is to uncover insights related to the dynamics of a specific research issue. The researcher categorized the responses into several prevalent themes. In qualitative research, thematic analysis is employed to present findings based

on the themes under which various responses can be classified. This method is particularly relevant for studies lacking a pre-existing theoretical framework to guide data design, making it suitable for investigations with diverse outcomes and no predetermined variables or constructs. Young (2018) notes that qualitative data analysis differs significantly from its quantitative counterpart, involving processes such as data reduction and display. Creswell (2018) further asserts that qualitative data collection and analysis occur simultaneously. Yin (2019) suggests that qualitative research should utilize pattern matching techniques derived from existing concepts and theories in the literature to effectively organize qualitative data. By analyzing qualitative data through themes, researchers ensure that the organization is not confined to predetermined categories, thereby allowing for a more comprehensive exploration of the results.

3.10 Ethical Consideration

Ethical consideration in academic research is a crucial factor that adds considerable weight to research findings. In ensuring this, the objective and purpose of the study were articulated to the respondents to avoid any possible misunderstanding. Anonymity and confidentiality were assured respondents with respect to answers provided. According to Podsakoff et al. (2003) these procedures should reduce people's evaluation apprehension and make them less likely to edit their responses to be more socially desirable, lenient, acquiescent and consistent with how the researcher wants them to respond.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Introduction

The results of the analysis of data collected using the interview guide are presented in this chapter. The analysis is based on the predetermined research objectives, which included, exploring the critical factors in ERP systems' implementation influencing users' perception of the system among SME; ascertaining the consequences of users' perception of ERP systems' implementation among SMEs; and determining the strategies for driving positive user perceptions towards ERP systems' implementation among SMEs.

4.2 Demographic Data of Respondents

4.2.1 Codes of Respondents

The table presents the demographic details of the 20 participants in the study, divided into SME owners and employees, each group consisting of ten individuals. A total of ten (10) SMEs were used for the study. The SME owners are represented by codes P01 to P10, while the staff employees are coded S01 to S10. The table also indicates the gender distribution within each group. Among the SME owners, seven participants are male, and three are female. The staff group has an equal gender distribution, with five males and five females. These codes ensure the anonymity of participants and will be used to reference their quotations in the study. This approach allows for a clear and organized presentation of the research findings, maintaining a balanced perspective from both SME owners and employees, which is essential for the comprehensive analysis of the study's subject matter.

Table 4. 1: Codes of Respondents

Code	Position	Gender
P01	SME Owner	Male
P02	SME Owner	Male
P03	SME Owner	Male
P04	SME Owner	Male
P05	SME Owner	Male
P06	SME Owner	Male
P07	SME Owner	Female
P08	SME Owner	Male
P09	SME Owner	Female
P10	SME Owner	Female
S01	Staff	Male
S02	Staff	Male
S03	Staff	Male
S04	Staff	Male
S05	Staff	Male
S06	Staff	Female
S07	Staff	Female
S08	Staff	Female
S09	Staff	Female
S10	Staff	Female

Source: Field Survey, 2024

4.2.2. Gender of Respondents

The gender composition of the respondents is shown in Table 4.2 below. The table provides the gender information which shows that 60% of the respondents were males while 40% of them were females. The survey shows that the majority of the respondents were males.

Table 4. 2: Gender Composition

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	12	60%
Female	8	40%
Total	20	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

4.2.3 Age Group of Respondents

Table 4.3 below shows the age distribution of the respondents. Out of the total respondents (15), 40% representing the majority were between the ages of 30-39 years, 20% were between 20-29 years whilst 20% were between the ages of 40-49 years. Also, 20% representing were 50 years and above.

Table 4. 3: Age Group of Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
20-29 years	4	20%
30-39 years	8	40%
40-49 years	4	20%
50 years and more	4	20%
Total	20	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

4.2.4 Number of Years Working with the SME

When asked how many years they have been working with the SME, 10% indicated that they have been working for 2 years and below, 40% indicated that they have been working for Cal Bank between 2 and 5 years while 30% said 6-10 years. Finally, 20% representing 20 persons indicated 10 years and above.

Table 4. 4: Number of Years as Working with the SME

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Under 2 years	2	10%
2-5years	8	40%
6-10 years	6	30%
10 years and above	4	20%
Total	20	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

4.2.5 Type of ERP System Used by the Company

Table 4.5 below shows the distribution of ERP systems used by companies in the sample. The most commonly used ERP system is SAP, which accounts for 35% of the companies. Oracle and Microsoft Dynamics follow, with 25% and 20% respectively. Infor and other systems are less common, each being used by 10% of the companies.

Table 4. 5: Type of ERP System Used by the Company

ERP System Type	Frequency	Percentage
SAP	7	35%
Oracle	5	25%
Microsoft Dynamics	4	20%
Infor	2	10%
Other	2	10%
Total	20	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

4.2.6 Duration of ERP System Usage by the Company

Table 4.6 below illustrates how long companies have been using their ERP systems. The majority of companies (40%) have been using their systems for 2-5 years, while 25% have used them for 6-10 years. Only 15% have used their ERP systems for 10 years or more, and 20% have been using them for less than 2 years.

Table 4. 6: Duration of ERP System Usage by the Company

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Under 2 years	4	20%
2-5 years	8	40%
6-10 years	5	25%
10 years and above	3	15%
Total	20	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

4.3 Presentation of Results Relative to Research Objectives

4.3.1 To examine the critical factors in ERP systems' implementation influencing users' perception of the system among SMEs

The objective sought to examine the critical factors in ERP systems' implementation influencing users' perception of the system among SMEs. From the interview it was ascertained that system functionality and usability, training, communication, management support and employee involvement in decision-making are the critical areas in ERP systems' implementation influencing users' perception of the system among SMEs.

4.3.1.1 System Functionality and Usability

System functionality and usability are key factors when using an ERP system. Users often judge the system based on how easy it was to use and how well it supports their tasks. For the staff in SMEs, a user-friendly system is one that allows them to perform their duties efficiently without constant technical difficulties. A well-designed ERP system can simplify complex tasks and make operations smoother. If the system is easy to understand, users can quickly learn to use it, reducing the time and effort needed for training. On the other hand, a complicated system can cause frustration and slow down daily operations.

A Staff stated:

The SAP system is easy to use. I learned to work with it in a few days, and now I can do my tasks much faster than before. Before the ERP system, I spent a lot of time on manual processes and fixing errors. Now, everything is automated, and I can focus on more important tasks. It has really improved my productivity and made my job easier (S03).

Another staff stated:

The system meets my work requirements well. It has all the features I need, and I rarely encounter any issues. Whenever I need to find information or generate reports, the system is quick and reliable. It has reduced the amount of time I spend searching for data and has made my work more efficient. Overall, I am very satisfied with the ERP system (S02).

An owner stated:

Since implementing the ERP system, we have noticed a significant improvement in our daily operations. The system is intuitive, and our employees were able to learn it quickly. This has led to a reduction in errors and an increase in productivity. The automated

processes have saved us a lot of time and effort, allowing us to focus on growing the business (P07).

Another owner remarked:

The ERP system has been a game-changer for our company. It meets all our requirements and has made our operations more efficient. The ability to generate accurate reports quickly has been particularly useful. We can now make informed decisions faster, which has positively impacted our bottom line. Overall, the system has exceeded our expectations (P08).

The ERP system has significantly transformed the company's operations, making it a crucial tool in enhancing efficiency and productivity. Streamlining processes and enabling quick access to accurate data have empowered the company to make well-informed decisions promptly. This has improved the speed and accuracy of reporting while directly impacting the company's financial performance positively. The system's ease of use plays a pivotal role in enhancing the work experience for staff. With an intuitive interface, employees perform their tasks more efficiently, reducing the frustration often associated with complex systems. This user-friendly nature fosters a more positive perception among the staff, leading to increased adoption and satisfaction. Overall, the ERP system exceeds expectations, meeting the company's operational needs while contributing to a more productive and satisfied workforce.

4.3.1.2 Training, Communication, and Management Support

Training, communication, and management support play a big role in how staff perceive the ERP system. Good training helps users understand the system better, while clear communication ensures everyone understands the goals and benefits of the new system. Management support

means identifying the staff's needs and concerns in order to make the necessary adjustment for effective system utilization and functionality.

Effective training programs make it easier for staff to adapt to the new system. When management communicates well, it helps staff feel more involved and informed. Support from management can also address any concerns or feedback, making the transition smoother.

A staff stated:

The technical support during our ERP training was always available and very helpful. Whenever I had a question or encountered a problem, the support team was quick to respond and provide a solution. They made sure we understood how to use the system and were patient with us during the learning process. It made the training experience much less stressful (S05).

Another staff indicated:

Management explained the benefits of the ERP system clearly and kept us informed throughout the implementation. They held regular meetings to update us on the progress and address any concerns we had. Their open communication helped build trust and made us feel more comfortable with the changes. Knowing that management was there to support us made a big difference (S08).

An owner stated:

The training provided during the ERP implementation was comprehensive and well-organized. Our employees received hands-on training, which helped them understand the system better. The technical support team was always available to assist with any issues,

making the transition less stressful. This level of support was crucial for a smooth implementation (P06).

Another owner stated,

Management played a key role in the success of the ERP implementation. They kept everyone informed about the progress and benefits of the new system. Regular meetings were held to address any concerns and gather feedback from employees. This open communication helped build trust and made the transition easier for everyone. Knowing that management was there to support us made a big difference (P07).

With strong training, communication, and support, staff and owners feel more confident and positive about using the ERP system. It helps them adapt more quickly and reduces resistance to the new system.

4.3.1.3 Employee Involvement in Decision-Making

Employee involvement in the decision-making process during ERP implementation can influence user perceptions. When staff are included in decisions, they feel valued and more willing to embrace the new system. Involving employees can also lead to better system customization that meets their specific needs. When staff have a say in the ERP implementation, they are more likely to support and use the system effectively. It also helps in identifying potential issues early on, making it easier to address them.

A staff stated:

We were asked for our input during the ERP implementation, which made me feel like my opinion mattered. Management held focus groups and surveys to gather our feedback and

used it to make decisions about the system's features and functions. It was nice to know that our voices were heard and that we had a role in shaping the system (S03).

An owner said:

Management listened to our feedback and made adjustments based on our needs. For example, we requested certain reports and features that were not initially included, and management worked with the ERP provider to add them. This made the system more useful for our daily tasks and showed that management cared about our needs and concerns (P05).

Including staff in decisions helps create a sense of ownership and acceptance of the ERP system, leading to a more streamlined implementation and improving overall satisfaction with the system.

4.3.2 To determine the consequences of users' perception of ERP systems' implementation among SMEs

The objective sought to determine the consequences of users' perception of ERP systems' implementation among SMEs. From the interview, it was discovered that positive perceptions of ERP system implementation among SMEs often result in increased efficiency and productivity, improved decision-making processes, and enhanced collaboration and information sharing across departments while negative perception of ERP system implementation stem from various factors, such as increased workload and stress, difficulties in using the system, and reduced morale and resistance to change among employees.

4.3.2.1 Positive Perception

Positive perceptions of ERP system implementation among SMEs often result in increased efficiency and productivity, improved decision-making processes, and enhanced collaboration and

information sharing across departments. When employees find the ERP system helpful, they are more likely to embrace it and use it to its full potential. This can lead to streamlined operations, faster data retrieval, and better coordination between different departments.

An effective ERP system can automate routine tasks, reduce manual errors, and provide real-time data that supports informed decision-making. Employees can access up-to-date information quickly, which helps them to make better decisions and respond more promptly to changes in the business environment. Additionally, the ERP system can foster better communication and collaboration by providing a centralized platform where all relevant data is accessible to everyone who needs it.

A staff stated:

Since the implementation of the ERP system, my efficiency and productivity have increased significantly. The system automates many of the routine tasks that used to take up a lot of my time, allowing me to focus on more important aspects of my job. I can now complete my work much faster and with fewer errors (S08).

An owner stated:

The ERP system has greatly influenced our decision-making processes. With real-time data at our fingertips, we can make more informed decisions quickly. This has not only improved our overall efficiency but also helped us to identify and address issues before they become major problems. It has been a game-changer for our business (P07).

Overall, a positive perception of the ERP system leads to better performance and more efficient operations, benefiting both employees and the business as a whole.

4.3.2.2 Negative Perception

Negative perceptions of ERP system implementation stem from various factors, such as increased workload and stress, difficulties in using the system, and reduced morale and resistance to change among employees. When the transition to an ERP system is not smooth, it causes frustration and negatively impact employees' attitudes toward the new system.

Employees may find the ERP system complicated or difficult to use, which increases their workload and stress levels. If the training provided is inadequate or if the system is not user-friendly, employees may struggle to adapt, leading to decreased productivity. Additionally, the change can be met with resistance if employees feel that the new system disrupts their established workflows or if they are not adequately involved in the decision-making process.

A staff stated:

The transition to the ERP system has significantly increased my workload and stress levels.

The system is not as intuitive as I had hoped, and it takes a lot of time to perform tasks that used to be simple. This has made my job more stressful and less enjoyable (S05).

Another staff mentioned,

There were several difficulties in using the ERP system. The training provided was insufficient, and I often find myself struggling to understand how to use certain features.

This has led to a lot of frustration and has negatively impacted my productivity. I feel less confident in my work now (S03).

A negative perception of the ERP system leads to decreased morale and increased resistance to change among employees, which hinders the overall success of the implementation. It is important for management to address these issues promptly and provide the necessary support to help employees adapt to the new system.

4.3.3 The strategies for driving positive user perceptions towards ERP systems' implementation among SMEs

The objective sought to examine the strategies for driving positive user perception towards ERP systems' implementation among SMEs. The study revealed that comprehensive training programs, effective communication and management support, involvement in decision-making and continuous improvement and feedback loops are the strategies for driving positive user perceptions towards ERP systems' implementation among SMEs.

4.3.3.1 Comprehensive Training Programs

Training is essential for driving positive perceptions of ERP systems among both owners and staff. Well-structured training programs ensure that all users are comfortable and proficient with the new system. This can include initial training sessions, ongoing support, and refresher courses. Providing continuous learning opportunities, employees can build confidence in using the ERP system, which helps in reducing resistance and increasing productivity.

A staff member stated:

Additional training sessions focusing on specific features of the ERP system would be very helpful. Sometimes, we only scratch the surface of what the system can do, and more in-depth training could help us utilize it better. Also, having access to a dedicated support team for questions and troubleshooting would make a big difference in our day-to-day use (S02).

An owner stated:

To improve our experience with the ERP system, ongoing training and support are crucial. Employees need to feel confident in their ability to use the system, and regular training sessions can help with that. Also, creating a knowledge base where users can find answers to common questions and issues would be beneficial (P06).

Providing training and support helps ensure that users are comfortable with the ERP system, leading to more efficient use and a positive perception overall.

4.3.3.2 Effective Communication and Management Support

Clear communication and strong management support are vital for fostering positive user perceptions of ERP systems. Management should communicate the benefits and goals of the ERP system clearly and frequently. This helps employees understand the value of the system and how it will benefit their work. Additionally, management should be actively involved in the implementation process, addressing any concerns and providing support where needed.

A staff member noted:

Management can encourage user adoption by regularly communicating the benefits of the ERP system and how it can make our work easier. Regular updates on the implementation process and success stories from other users can also motivate us to use the system more effectively. It's important that management shows they are invested in the system's success and our comfort with it (S10).

An owner remarked:

Management should be transparent about the goals of the ERP system and how it aligns with the company's vision. They should also be proactive in addressing any concerns from

employees and providing the necessary support. Regular check-ins and feedback sessions can help ensure that everyone is on the same page and that any issues are resolved promptly (P02).

Strong communication and management support help create a positive environment for ERP system adoption, ensuring that employees feel valued and understood throughout the process.

4.3.3.3 Involvement in Decision-Making

Involving employees in the decision-making process during ERP implementation can lead to higher acceptance and satisfaction. When employees have a say in the selection and customization of the system, they are more likely to embrace it. This can be done through surveys, focus groups, and pilot programs where employees can test the system and provide input.

An employee mentioned:

Being involved in the decision-making process for the ERP system made me feel valued and more willing to use the system. We had the opportunity to provide feedback and suggest features that would be beneficial for our daily tasks. This involvement made the transition smoother and helped us feel more connected to the new system (S04).

An owner stated:

Including employees in the decision-making process is key to ensuring a successful ERP implementation. When employees feel that their opinions are valued, they are more likely to support the system and use it effectively. This also helps in identifying potential issues early on and making necessary adjustments before full implementation (P10).

Employee involvement in decision-making fosters a sense of ownership and acceptance, leading to a more positive perception of the ERP system.

4.3.3.4 Continuous Improvement and Feedback Loops

After the initial implementation, it is important to continually seek feedback from users and make necessary adjustments. Regularly updating the system based on user feedback can help address any issues and improve the overall user experience. This ongoing process shows that management is committed to making the ERP system work for everyone.

A staff stated:

Regular feedback sessions and updates based on our suggestions make me feel that my input is valued. When management acts on our feedback and makes improvements, it shows that they are committed to making the ERP system work for us. This continuous improvement process helps in addressing any issues and enhances our overall experience with the system (S03).

An owner noted,

Implementing a feedback loop where employees can share their experiences and suggestions for the ERP system is essential. This helps in identifying areas for improvement and ensures that the system evolves to meet the needs of the users. Regular updates and enhancements based on feedback demonstrate that management is listening and taking action to improve the system (P09).

Continuous improvement and feedback loops help ensure that the ERP system remains effective and user-friendly, leading to sustained positive perceptions among users.

4.4 Discussion of findings

4.4.1 To examine the critical factors in ERP systems' implementation influencing users' perception of the system among SMEs

The objective sought to examine the critical factors in ERP systems' implementation influencing users' perception of the system among SMEs. The study revealed that system functionality and usability, training, communication, and management support and employee involvement in decision-making are the critical in ERP systems' implementation influencing users' perception of the system among SMEs. There are substantial evidences in the empirical literature that aligns with this finding like Bettinger and Fox (2019), Loeb and Taylor (2017), Broadbent (2017) and many others.

The importance of system functionality and usability, as highlighted in this study, aligns with the work of Bettinger and Fox (2019). Their research underscores that when systems or platforms are designed with clear, structured content and are user-friendly, users are more likely to have a positive perception of them. In the context of ERP systems, this translates to a need for interfaces that are intuitive and functionalities that align closely with the users' everyday tasks. A system that is both functional and usable reduces the cognitive load on users, making it easier for them to perform their tasks efficiently, which in turn enhances their overall perception of the system.

The critical role of training in shaping users' perceptions of ERP systems is supported by the findings of Loeb and Taylor (2017). They indicated that well-structured training programs significantly improve users' ability to navigate and effectively utilize new systems. In ERP implementations, comprehensive training ensures that users are comfortable with the system's functionalities and can maximize its potential. This directly impacts their satisfaction and

perception, as they feel more confident and capable in their interactions with the system. The alignment of this study with Loeb and Taylor's findings highlights the necessity of investing in thorough and ongoing training programs as part of ERP system rollouts.

Broadbent (2017) also contributes to this discussion by pointing out the essential role of communication in the successful adoption of new technologies. According to Broadbent, clear and consistent communication during the implementation process helps in setting realistic expectations and reducing resistance to change. This is particularly relevant in the context of ERP systems in SMEs, where effective communication can bridge the gap between the technical aspects of the system and the users' everyday experiences. When users are well-informed about what to expect and how to address potential challenges, their perception of the system becomes more favorable. The importance of management support and employee involvement in decision-making, as identified in this study, resonates with the findings of Davies and Graff (2015). Their research highlighted that support from leadership and active involvement of employees in decision-making processes are crucial for the successful adoption of new systems. When employees feel that their input is valued and that management is committed to supporting them through the transition, they are more likely to engage positively with the system. This finding is particularly relevant in SMEs, where the organizational structure often allows for more direct involvement of employees in strategic decisions.

The flexibility to learn at one's own pace, as discussed by Dumford and Miller (2018), is another factor that aligns with the current study's emphasis on training. Their work suggests that when users can control the pace of their learning, they are more likely to stay engaged and achieve better

outcomes. In ERP implementations, this could be translated into providing users with the resources and time they need to familiarize themselves with the system at their own pace, thus enhancing their perception of the system's usability.

Hurlbut (2018) and Al-Musawi (2022) further support the findings of this study by emphasizing the importance of providing adequate resources to users during system implementation. Hurlbut's research pointed out that the availability of supportive resources, such as detailed manuals, helpdesks, and ongoing technical support, is crucial for user satisfaction and success. Al-Musawi (2022) extends this by showing that when systems are designed with user support in mind, users are more likely to perceive the system positively. This is particularly important in ERP systems, where the complexity of the system requires ongoing support to ensure that users can effectively navigate and utilize the system.

4.4.2 To determine the consequences of users' perception of ERP systems' implementation among SMEs

The objective sought to determine the consequences of users' perception of ERP systems' implementation among SMEs. The study revealed that positive perceptions of ERP system implementation among SMEs often result in increased efficiency and productivity, improved decision-making processes, and enhanced collaboration and information sharing across departments while negative perception of ERP system implementation stem from various factors, such as increased workload and stress, difficulties in using the system, and reduced morale and resistance to change among employees.

The study's findings on the impact of ERP system implementation in SMEs are in line with several other research studies. Cappel and Hayen (2020) found that when employees have a positive view of ERP systems, it often leads to greater efficiency, better productivity, and improved decision-making in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Their study showed that when employees understand and support the system, it makes it easier for different departments to work together and share information, which helps the business run more smoothly. This is similar to the current study, where positive perceptions of ERP systems among SMEs lead to better performance across the board.

Filimban (2018) studied the implementation of ERP systems in the Middle East and discovered that positive employee attitudes towards these systems resulted in more efficient business processes and higher productivity. Employees who felt that the system made their jobs easier were more likely to use it effectively, which contributed to the overall success of the business. This finding supports the idea that positive perceptions of ERP systems can have a strong impact on a company's performance.

Garrison and Anderson (2023) looked at the impact of ERP systems in small businesses in North America. They found that when employees believed in the benefits of the ERP system, it led to better collaboration and communication between departments. This, in turn, improved the decision-making process and helped the company respond more quickly to changes in the market. The results from their study are consistent with the current research, which also found that positive perceptions of ERP systems lead to improved communication and decision-making. Haitham (2019) conducted research on ERP systems in Southeast Asia and found that negative perceptions

often stemmed from factors like increased workload, stress, and difficulties in using the system. Employees who struggled with the new system were more likely to resist it, which reduced morale and made the implementation process more challenging. This matches the findings of the current study, where negative perceptions of ERP systems were linked to similar issues. Kirby, Sharpe, and Barbour (2017) examined the challenges of ERP system implementation in small businesses and found that employees who faced difficulties in learning the new system often felt overwhelmed and stressed. This led to resistance to the system and a decrease in overall productivity. Their research highlighted the importance of providing proper training and support to ensure a smooth transition. This aligns with the current study's finding that negative perceptions of ERP systems are often due to challenges in using the system and the stress that comes with it.

Leshowitz (2023) studied ERP systems in European SMEs and found that employee resistance to change was a major barrier to successful implementation. Employees who were comfortable with the old ways of doing things often saw the new system as a threat, leading to lower morale and productivity. This is consistent with the current study's finding that negative perceptions of ERP systems can lead to resistance to change and a negative impact on performance.

DiCerbo and Symington (2019) explored the impact of ERP systems on small businesses in Australia and found that businesses with positive perceptions of the system experienced better collaboration across departments. Employees who saw the system as beneficial were more likely to work together effectively, leading to improved information sharing and decision-making. This supports the current study's findings that positive views of ERP systems lead to better collaboration and overall business performance.

4.4.3 The strategies for driving positive user perceptions towards ERP systems' implementation among SMEs

The objective sought to examine the strategies for driving positive user perception towards ERP systems' implementation among SMEs. The study revealed that comprehensive training programs, effective communication and management support, involvement in decision-making and continuous improvement and feedback loops are the strategies for driving positive user perceptions towards ERP systems' implementation among SMEs.

This is supported by various other research studies. Dase (2024) found that when employees receive thorough training on ERP systems, they are more likely to understand and accept the changes brought by the new system. This training helps them feel more confident in using the system, which reduces resistance and increases productivity. This aligns with the current study, which also emphasizes the importance of comprehensive training programs in creating positive perceptions of ERP systems.

Eyitomi and Taiwo (2018) researched ERP implementation in Nigerian SMEs and discovered that clear and consistent communication throughout the implementation process plays a crucial role in ensuring that employees understand the benefits of the system. They found that when management communicates openly and regularly with employees, it helps to address concerns and build trust, leading to a smoother implementation process. This finding matches the current study's emphasis on effective communication as a strategy for driving positive perceptions.

Kayani and Arslan (2018) studied ERP adoption in Pakistani SMEs and highlighted the importance of management support during the implementation phase. They found that when employees feel supported by management, they are more likely to embrace the new system. Management can show support by providing resources, addressing concerns, and being actively involved in the implementation process. This is consistent with the current study, which also identifies management support as a critical factor in shaping positive user perceptions.

Korenková, Závadský, and Lis (2019) examined ERP systems in European SMEs and found that involving employees in decision-making processes related to the system's implementation can lead to higher levels of acceptance and satisfaction. When employees feel that their opinions are valued and that they have a say in how the system is implemented, they are more likely to support the change. This is in line with the current study's recommendation for involving employees in decision-making as a strategy for improving perceptions.

Nawawi, Agustia, Lusnadi, and Fauzi (2020) researched ERP implementation in Southeast Asian SMEs and noted the importance of continuous improvement and feedback loops. They found that collecting regular feedback from employees and making adjustments based on that feedback helps to keep the system aligned with the needs of the users. This ongoing process of improvement ensures that the system remains user-friendly and effective, which encourages positive perceptions among employees. The current study similarly emphasizes the role of continuous feedback in maintaining positive user perceptions.

Said, Joseph, and Sidek (2017) looked into ERP systems in Malaysian SMEs and found that when employees are actively involved in providing feedback on the system's performance, it leads to higher satisfaction and better system adoption. This involvement helps to identify any issues early on and allows for quick adjustments, which keeps the system working smoothly and users happy. This finding supports the current study's recommendation for continuous feedback and improvement. Uwuigbe and Asiriwa (2020) studied ERP implementation in African SMEs and highlighted the role of management in ensuring a successful rollout. They found that when management takes an active role in supporting employees throughout the process, it reduces resistance and increases the likelihood of successful adoption. This aligns with the current study, which also points out the importance of management support.

Uwuigbe and Teddy (2019) focused on ERP systems in Nigerian SMEs and found that clear communication from management about the benefits and goals of the system helps to reduce uncertainty and resistance among employees. When employees understand why the system is being implemented and how it will benefit the organization, they are more likely to support it. This supports the current study's findings on the need for effective communication. Zaman and Bahadar (2021) examined ERP systems in South Asian SMEs and found that training, communication, and feedback are essential for ensuring that employees perceive the system positively. Their study highlighted that when these elements are in place, employees are more likely to see the system as a tool that improves their work rather than as a burden. This aligns well with the current study's recommendations for strategies to drive positive user perceptions of ERP systems in SMEs.

4.5 Chapter Summary

This chapter presents analysis of the data collected through interviewing the owners and Staffs of the selected SMEs in Accra. This Chapter identified several critical factors influencing users' perceptions of ERP systems, including system functionality and usability, training, communication, management support, and employee involvement in decision-making. The consequences of these perceptions were found to be significant. Positive perceptions led to increased efficiency, improved decision-making, and enhanced collaboration across departments. Conversely, negative perceptions resulted in increased workload and stress, difficulties in system usage, and resistance to change.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Introduction

The summary of findings, conclusions, and study recommendations are presented in this chapter. The study's results are summarized in the chapter, along with any recommendations deemed appropriate. This chapter also examines the study's limitations and offers suggestions for future research.

5.2 Research Summary

The core objective of this research was to find out the key variables in the ERP implementation process which do influence users' perception of ERP adoption among SMEs. An interview guide with predetermined questions based on the research objectives was the main tool used for data collection. A total of twenty (20) individuals constituted the sample size of the study thus ten (10) SME owners and ten (10) employees of the selected companies. Descriptive tools were used for the demographics of the respondents, but the research objectives were analyzed using thematic analysis thus the collected data were transcribed and grouped based on the trend of the answers.

Findings of the first objective revealed that system functionality and usability, training, communication, and management support and employee involvement in decision-making are the critical in ERP systems' implementation influencing users' perception of the system among SMEs. On the second objective, it was discovered that that positive perceptions of ERP system implementation among SMEs often result in increased efficiency and productivity, improved decision-making processes, and enhanced collaboration and information sharing across departments whiles negative perception of ERP system implementation stem from various factors,

such as increased workload and stress, difficulties in using the system, and reduced morale and resistance to change among employees.

On the third and final objective, the study revealed that comprehensive training programs, effective communication and management support, involvement in decision-making and continuous improvement and feedback loops are the strategies for driving positive user perceptions towards ERP systems' implementation among SMEs.

5.3 Conclusions of the Study

On the basis of the findings, the researcher concludes that;

The findings from the study allow us to understand some key points about ERP system implementation among SMEs. First, the functionality and usability of the system, along with proper training, communication, and support from management, are very important. When these elements are present, employees tend to have a more favorable view of the system.

Second, how employees perceive the system can greatly impact the overall success of its implementation. Positive perceptions usually lead to better efficiency, improved decision-making, and stronger teamwork across departments. On the other hand, if employees see the system as difficult to use or feel overwhelmed by it, their morale may drop, and they might resist the changes. Finally, to ensure that employees view the system in a positive light, it's necessary to provide thorough training, maintain open communication, involve them in decision-making, and regularly seek their feedback. These steps can help build a supportive environment where employees feel comfortable using the new system, leading to a more successful implementation.

5.4 Recommendations of the Study

From the findings of this research work and the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are deemed appropriate by the researcher:

5.4.1 Recommendation for Finding 1

The study found that system functionality, usability, proper training, communication, and management support are key to the successful implementation of ERP systems in SMEs. To improve these areas, a few recommendations can be made. First, when selecting an ERP system, businesses should focus on choosing software that is user-friendly and aligns with their daily operations. The system should have features that are easy to understand and use, so employees can perform their tasks without frustration. Involving end-users in the selection process could help ensure that the chosen system meets their needs and expectations.

Second, training programs must be thorough and tailored to the different roles within the company. Rather than one-time sessions, ongoing training should be provided, allowing employees to develop their skills over time. This approach can reduce the learning curve and make employees more comfortable with the new system. Practical, hands-on training sessions that simulate real-world tasks can help employees gain confidence in using the ERP system.

Third, clear communication is essential during the ERP implementation process. Regular updates about the project's progress, expected challenges, and benefits should be shared with all employees. This transparency can help manage expectations and reduce anxiety about the changes. Employees should also have channels to ask questions and voice concerns throughout the process.

Management support is also critical. Leaders need to actively promote the new system and show their commitment to its success. They should be available to address any issues that arise and provide the necessary resources to ensure the project stays on track. By being involved and supportive, management can encourage a positive attitude among employees, which can contribute to a smoother implementation process.

Finally, involving employees in decision-making related to the ERP system can increase their sense of ownership and acceptance. When employees feel that their opinions matter and that they are part of the process, they are more likely to embrace the changes and work towards making the system a success. Regular feedback sessions where employees can share their experiences and suggest improvements can help fine-tune the system to better meet the company's needs.

5.4.2 Recommendation for Finding 2

The second finding shows that employees' perceptions of ERP systems can greatly affect the outcome of the implementation. Positive perceptions tend to lead to better efficiency, improved decision-making, and enhanced collaboration. To cultivate these positive perceptions, several steps can be taken.

First, communication is key. Employees should be informed about the benefits of the new system before it is implemented. This could be done through workshops, meetings, or informational materials that explain how the ERP system will improve their work and the overall performance of the company. If employees understand the benefits, they are more likely to view the system positively.

Second, it is essential to address the concerns and fears that employees might have about the new system. Change can be stressful, and employees might worry about increased workloads, job security, or their ability to learn the new system. Holding open forums where employees can express their concerns and receive honest answers can help alleviate some of these worries. Addressing concerns directly and providing support can make employees feel more secure and willing to accept the changes.

Third, to prevent negative perceptions from taking root, it is important to manage the implementation process carefully. The system should be introduced gradually, allowing employees to adjust at their own pace. Any issues that arise during the transition should be dealt with promptly to avoid frustration. If employees encounter problems and feel that their concerns are not being addressed, they may develop a negative view of the system.

Fourth, recognizing and rewarding employees who adapt well to the new system can encourage others to do the same. Positive reinforcement, such as praise or small incentives, can motivate employees to embrace the ERP system. When employees see that their efforts are appreciated, they are more likely to develop a positive attitude toward the changes.

Lastly, creating a supportive environment where employees can help each other learn the new system can foster a sense of teamwork. Peer-to-peer learning sessions or mentoring programs where more experienced users help others can reduce the feeling of isolation that some employees

might experience during the transition. This approach not only helps build confidence but also strengthens the overall team spirit.

5.4.3 Recommendation for Finding 3

The third finding revealed that strategies like comprehensive training, effective communication, management support, involvement in decision-making, and continuous improvement are essential for driving positive user perceptions of ERP systems. To implement these strategies successfully, several actions can be recommended.

First, comprehensive training programs should be designed to meet the specific needs of different user groups within the organization. Training should not be a one-size-fits-all approach. Instead, it should cater to the varying levels of experience and responsibilities of employees. Offering basic training for beginners and more advanced sessions for experienced users can ensure that everyone is well-prepared to use the system. Providing access to resources like user manuals, video tutorials, and online forums can also help employees continue learning at their own pace.

Second, communication during and after the ERP implementation process is crucial. Regular updates about the progress of the implementation, upcoming changes, and how the system will benefit the company should be communicated clearly to all employees. This transparency helps build trust and keeps employees informed about what to expect. Open channels for communication, such as suggestion boxes or regular meetings, allow employees to share their feedback and concerns, ensuring that they feel heard and valued.

Third, management support plays a key role in the success of an ERP system. Leaders should actively participate in the implementation process, showing their commitment to the project and providing the necessary resources. Management should also be approachable, offering support and guidance whenever employees face challenges. Their involvement helps set a positive tone for the entire organization, encouraging employees to embrace the changes.

Fourth, involving employees in decision-making processes related to the ERP system can increase their engagement and acceptance. When employees are given a voice in decisions that affect their work, they are more likely to feel ownership over the system and work towards its success. Regular meetings where employees can provide input and suggest improvements can help tailor the system to better meet the needs of the organization.

Finally, continuous improvement and feedback loops are necessary to maintain the effectiveness of the ERP system. The implementation process should not end once the system is in place. Regular reviews of the system's performance, along with feedback from employees, can help identify areas for improvement. Making adjustments based on this feedback ensures that the system continues to meet the needs of the business and its employees. Encouraging a culture of continuous learning and adaptation can help the organization stay agile and responsive to changes in the business environment.

5.5 Limitations to the study

The study's breadth is constrained because it did not adequately cover a lot of SMEs. It covered just the views of some few owners and staff which limits the scope. This study used a sample of ten (10) SME owners and ten (10) employees of the selected companies. This limits the findings

since the findings could be subjective to the personal views of those interviewed. Access to data was a significant obstacle the researcher faced while doing this study. Primary data was quite difficult to access because the participants had busy schedules and as a result some of responders were unavailable to engage. Despite all these limitations the researcher was able to collect the data by scheduling convenient times for interviewing participants and considered using technology such as Video calls to overcome long distance limitations. Also, developing a rapport with the participants helped build trust by clearly explaining the research purpose and process enhancing the quality of data. Participant confidentiality was a top priority of the researcher which enabled staffs and SMEs owners to willingly share sensitive information hence reducing the risks of negative consequences from participating in this research.

5.6 Suggestion for Future studies

This research proposes that future research could consider widening the scope of the research to include a lot of SMEs owners and staff to help make the findings strong and possible to be generalized.

5.7 Chapter Summary

This final chapter provides a comprehensive overview of the study's outcomes. It summarizes the key findings, presents conclusions based on the research objectives, and emphasizes the study's significant contributions. Additionally, it offers pertinent recommendations for Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system implementation, practical applications, and future research directions.

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APPENDIX A

JONATHAN HODZI

UNIVERSITY OF GHANA BUSINESS SCHOOL

DEPARTMENT OF OPERATIONS AND MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEMS

INTERVIEW GUIDE – SME's STAFF

Dear Sir/Madam,

I am Jonathan Hodzi, an MBA student at the University of Ghana Business School pursuing Management Information Systems. I am conducting my final year long essay in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of my degree. The title of my long essay is **“IMPLEMENTATION OF ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANNING SYSTEMS AMONG SMES: USER PERCEPTIONS AND ITS IMPLICATIONS ON BUSINESS PERFORMANCE.”**

Your candid responses will be highly appreciated. By participating in this interview, you indicate that you voluntarily wish to participate in this research. Please be rest assured that the information to be gathered from you is purely intended for academic purposes only. You may reach me via email at **jhodzi004@st.ug.edu.gh** or phone me on **0540936278**.

Thank you.

Section A - Background Information

1. What is the highest educational level you have completed?
2. How many years have you been working in this company?
3. What is your position in the company?

Section B – ERP Implementation Experience

4. What type of ERP system is your company using?
5. How long have you been using the ERP system?

Section C – Critical factors Influencing User Perceptions:

System functionality & Usability

6. What are your thoughts on the ERP system's user friendliness and overall usability?
7. In what ways has the ERP system supported your specific work requirements and expectations?

Training, communication, and Management Support

8. Can you describe the availability and efficiency of technical support during your ERP system training?
9. How would you describe management's approach to communication regarding the goals and benefits of the ERP system implementation?
10. Can you describe the level of employee involvement in the decision-making process during the ERP implementation?
11. How effectively did management address user concerns and feedback regarding the ERP system?

Section D - Consequences of User Perceptions

Positive Perception

12. How has the ERP system implementation increased your efficiency and productivity in your work?
13. In what ways has the ERP system influenced your decision-making processes?
14. How has the ERP system enhanced collaboration and information sharing across departments?

Negative Perception

15. In what ways has the transition to the ERP system affected your workload and stress?
16. What were some of the difficulties in using the ERP system?
17. Did the ERP system reduce morale and resistance to change among employees?

SECTION E: Strategies for Driving Positive Perceptions

18. What additional training or support would be helpful for improving your experience with the ERP system?
19. How can management better encourage user adoption and positive perception of the ERP system?
20. In your opinion, what are some key strategies for ensuring a smooth and successful ERP implementation in terms of user perception?

APPENDIX B

JONATHAN HODZI

UNIVERSITY OF GHANA BUSINESS SCHOOL

DEPARTMENT OF OPERATIONS AND MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEMS

INTERVIEW GUIDE – SME's OWNERS

Dear Sir/Madam,

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Thank you.

Section A - Background Information

1. How long have you been in business?
2. What are your core business functions?
3. What are your experiences in using enterprise resource planning systems?

Section B - To examine the critical factors in ERP systems' implementation influencing users' perception of the system among SMEs.

4. As an SME owner what are the critical factors in ERP systems' implementation influencing your perception of the system?
5. What role do technical support and training play in shaping users' experiences with ERP systems?
6. How does your organizational culture influence ERP system implementation?

Section C - To determine the consequences and outcomes of users' perception of ERP systems' implementation among SMEs?

7. In your opinion, what are the consequences and outcomes of your perception of ERP systems' implementation in your SMEs?
8. As an SME owner, how has the implementation of the ERP system affected decision-making processes within your company?
9. Describe the impact of user's perception of the ERP system on their daily work routines?

Section D - What are the strategies for driving positive user perceptions towards ERP systems' implementation among SMEs?

10. In your opinion, what recommendations would you make for developing strategies to drive positive user perceptions of ERP systems in SMEs?
11. What are the perceived benefits of involving employees in the ERP system selection and implementation process, as an SME owner?
12. How can SMEs foster a positive user experience and encourage user adoption of ERP systems?

Thank You